

THE ROLE OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE IN STOCK RETURN MODELS OF LQ45 INDEXED COMPANIES

ROSDIANA^{1*}, AYU PUSPITANINGTYAS², LUQMAN HAKIM³ and YULI ZAIN⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Persada Indonesia Y.A.I.

Email: ¹Rosdiana.2266390003@upi-yai.ac.id (*Corresponding Author), ²Ayu.2266390002@upi-yai.ac.id,

³luqman.hakim@upi-yai.ac.id, ⁴yuli.zain@upi-yai.ac.id

Abstract

This study is to analyze and answer the inconsistency of previous research results and explain the Market Appreciation phenomenon which is different from the Efficient Capital Market theory. This is what prompted the researcher to do it by using a combination of time series and cross sectional. This type of research is quantitative with multiple regression analysis method of panel data with a sample of 27 LQ-45 indexed companies for five years. The formula in this study, maximizes the Market Appreciation value through the Company's Capital Structure as an intervening variable and by using the research object of the company on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Two research models are integrated into one and each through model selection testing, Chow Test, Hausman Test, and Lagrange Multiplier Test. The results of the first model; Increasing the Company's Financial Performance has an effect on increasing the Company's Capital Structure, these results confirm that this is not in accordance with the theory. Similar results also occur in Company Liquidity which affects the Company's Capital Structure with a positive correlation and this also contradicts the theory. The results of the second research model are not much different from the first model, Company Financial Performance and Company Liquidity each have an effect on Market Appreciation, but these results support the existing theory. The Company's Capital Structure as an intervening variable cannot mediate Market Appreciation so it cannot be used as a reference to predict it. It is hoped that these results can help as a guideline for investors on the Indonesia Stock Exchange to obtain maximum Stock Returns.

Keywords: Company Financial Performance, Shareholders' Income, Company Liquidity, Company Capital Structure Ratio, Market Appreciation.

INTRODUCTION

The Efficient Market Hypothesis theory states that the stock prices formed are a reflection of all existing information, both fundamental and insider information. In Statman (1998) states that investors cannot beat market returns systematically and stock prices are rational. What is meant by rational is that stock prices reflect fundamentals such as risk value and do not reflect psychological aspects such as investor sentiment. In Fama (1970), the concept of an efficient market means that current stock prices reflect all available information. This means that information comes from past and present information and is supplemented by information from the company itself (insider information). Research on the influence of profitability on stock returns finds different results and directions. The research results of Rahayu (2021) found that profitability had no effect on stock returns, while the research results of Anisa (2015), Legiman et al. (2015) and Subalno (2010) found that profitability has an effect on stock returns, then in Sudarsono & Sudiyatno (2016) found that profitability has a negative effect on stock returns, this negative effect means that the greater the profitability, the smaller the stock return and vice versa. the smaller the profitability, the greater the stock return, while Haanurat (2013), Putri &

Sampurno (2012), Wulandari et al. (2017), Utami & Murwaningsari (2017) and Martono (2016) found that profitability has a positive effect on stock returns, the greater the profitability, the greater the stock return and vice versa, the smaller the profitability, the smaller the stock return. This research is intended to carry out analysis and obtain confirmation of answers to the variables used in this research as endogenous variables, namely return on Assets (ROA), Earnings per Share (EPS), Liquidity Current Ratio and the intervening variable Leverage Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) influences the Stock Return (SR) variable. Market-based financial measures are financial ratios used to predict stock returns, where this ratio focuses on market information as the basis for analysis, in other words, this ratio is also called the market ratio. Ratios of market-based financial measures that are capable/feasible to explain stock returns include the price to earnings ratio (PER) in Muhammad & Scrimgeour (2014). According to Masa'deh, Tayeh, Al-Jarrah, & Tarhini (2015) PER is the result of a comparison between price per share and income per share. A small PER value indicates that the share price is cheap for investors to buy, but this indicates that the performance per share of the company is getting better in generating profits. In this way, it will attract investors' interest in buying the shares in question. This is stated in Zeytino, Akarim, & Çelik (2012) who in their research explains that market-based ratios are widely used by investors to determine market value. An issuer.

Apart from that, investors can also predict the real value of a share by using market-based ratios, one of which is PER. If the real value of a share is greater than its market value, then investors are interested in buying this type of share. Therefore, market-based ratios are a very important indicator in making investment decisions. Research conducted by Margaretha & Damayanti (2008) found that PER has a positive effect on stock returns. However, this is different from the research results presented by Carlo (2014) which stated that PER has no effect on stock returns. Thus, there are differences in research results regarding the relationship between PER and stock returns. For capital market players, whether for the long term or short term, Stock Return is an important factor in determining their choice to buy shares in the capital market. The return obtained can be in the form of capital gain/loss or yield, the higher the return obtained from a company's shares, the more attractive the investment in that share. In Utami & Murwaningsari (2017) that the dividend payout ratio has a significant effect with a positive correlation to stock returns but on the contrary by Devaki (2017), Puspitasari & Purnamasari (2013), Sayidah & Handayani (2017) that the dividend payout ratio has an insignificant effect on stock returns. Apart from dividend policy, profitability is also positive information for capital market players so it can influence stock returns.

The results of research conducted by Subalno (2010), Anisa (2015), Legiman et al. (2015), Putri & Sampurno (2012), Haanurat (2013), Wulandari et al. (2017) with the result that Return on Assets has a positive correlation with stock returns. Different results in Sudarsono & Sudiyatno (2016) with the result that Return on Assets has a significant effect with a negative correlation to stock returns. Apart from the dividend pay-out ratio and profitability factors, there are other factors that can have an impact on stock returns, namely company leverage. In the results of research by Putri & Sampurno (2012), Anisa (2015) with the results that the Debt to Equity Ratio has a significant effect with a negative correlation to stock returns, while in Sudarsono & Sudiyatno (2016) the results show that the Debt to Equity Ratio has an effect

significantly with a positive correlation to stock returns. Very different results in Subalno (2010), Haanurat (2013), Legiman et al. (2015), Wulandari et al. (2017), that Debt to Equity Ratio leverage has an insignificant effect on stock returns. The results of this research are as explained in the previous paragraph.

LITERATURE REVIEW DAN HIPOTESIS

Alternative sources of funds for determining policy are considered very important, because from various sources of funds there are capital costs that are not the same from one another. Therefore, company management considers it necessary to consider optimal balance in determining its capital structure, in the sense that there are various sources of funds so it is necessary to determine the source of funds from shares, debt, or a combination of both, Adi (2017). The results of research in Mulyani (2014) show that Return on Assets (ROA) has a significant effect with a positive correlation to capital structure (DER). However, different correlation results are found in Purwohandoko (2017) that Return on Assets (ROA) has a significant effect with a negative correlation to Capital Structure (DER).

H₁: Company financial performance affects the company's capital structure.

The research results in Reni (2014), Chen & Chou (2015) show that EPS has a significant effect with a positive correlation. The large fluctuations in the value of a company's earnings per share (EPS) can affect its capital structure.

H₂: Shareholders' income affects the company's capital structure.

In Nastiti (2016) liquidity has a significant effect with a positive correlation to Capital Structure (DER). Different correlation results in Bhattarai (2016), Verena and Haryanto (2013), Sheikh and Zongjun (2011), Nugrahani and Sampurno (2010), that liquidity has a significant effect with a negative correlation to capital structure. so that companies that have high liquidity can strengthen their capital internally, not from debt.

H₃: Company liquidity affects the company's capital structure.

In Anwaar (2016), Salamat and Mustafa (2016), Widyanti, Erna, dan Rina Trisnawati, (2021), Mujino, Adi Wijaya, (2021), Wijaya (2014), ROA has a significant effect with a positive correlation with stock returns. On the other hand, in Sudarsono and Sudiyatno (2016), Mahmudah and Suwitho (2016), Putri, Deasy dan Edric Kurniadi (2022), ROA has an insignificant effect on Stock Return.

H₄: There is an influence of the company's financial performance on market appreciation.

In the research results of Mayuni, IAI and Suarjaya, Gede (2018), Febriana, Febby and Sulistiana, Indra (2024), earnings per share have a significant effect on stock returns. Different results by Sinambela, Elizar, (2013), Febriana, Febby and Sulistiana, Indra (2024), Fitrianingih, Dwi et.al., (2022), Nurrohman MHN and Zulaikha (2013), that earnings per share have an insignificant effect on stock returns.

H₅: There is an influence of shareholder income on market appreciation

In Utami et al. (2015), Liquidity has a significant effect with a negative correlation on Stock Return. However, in Anwaar (2016), Maulida, Alfiatul, dan Maria Evania Karak, (2021), Yuwono, Wisnu, dan Dita Aurelia (2021), Bararoh (2015), liquidity has an insignificant effect on Stock Return.

H₆: There is an influence of company liquidity on market appreciation

The research results of Anisa (2015), Sudarsono & Sudiyatno (2016) show that leverage has a significant effect with a positive correlation on Stock Return, while in Putri & Sampurno (2012) it shows that leverage has a significant effect with a negative correlation on Stock Return. On the other hand, in the research results of Haanurat (2013), Legiman et. al. (2015), Subalno (2010), Wulandari et al. (2017), Hatfield et al. (1994) that leverage has an insignificant effect on Stock Return.

In the research results conducted by Sudiyatno, Bambang; and Elen Puspitasari, (2010), Nurwulandari, I Made Adnyana and Novi Loviana (2020), Sulhan, Muhammad; and Ahmad Sidi Pratomo, (2020), Suwardika, I Nyoman Agus and I Ketut Mustanda, (2017), Umam, Danang Choirul, and Imar Halimah, (2021), Onanjiri, Maulida, Alfiatul, and Maria Evania Karak, (2021), Richard Ndibanla; and Korankye, Thomas, (2014), Yuwono, Wisnu, and Dita Aurelia (2021), Murtini, Ni Kadek; and Ida Ayu Ratih Manuari (2021), the results of their research show that capital structure has a significant effect on stock returns. Meanwhile, different results were obtained by Siahaan, Fadjar O.P., (2013), the results of his research showed that capital structure had no significant effect on stock returns.

H₇: There is an influence of the company's capital structure on market appreciation

Figure 1: Research Drawing Framework Model

RESEARCH METHODS

The approach used in this study is quantitative with multiple regression analysis method of panel data using a combination of time series data for five years or the period 2015 - 2019 and cross section.

The objects used in this study are companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange and the population is companies included in the LQ-45 index group. From this population, the researcher then used a purposive sampling technique to produce 27 companies as research samples.

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables

No	Variables	Notation	Formula
1	Company Financial Performance	ROA _{it}	$\frac{\text{Earnings After Tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
2	Shareholders' Income	EPS _{it}	$\frac{\text{Net Income}_{it} - \text{Preferred Dividends}_{it}}{\text{Weighted Average Shares Outstanding}_{it}}$
3	Company Liquidity	CR _{it}	$\frac{\text{Current Assets}_{it}}{\text{Current Liabilities}_{it}}$
4	Company Capital Structure	DER _{it}	$\frac{\text{Debt}_{it}}{\text{Equity}_{it}}$
5	Market Appreciation	SR _{it}	$\frac{\text{Closing Price}_{it} - \text{Closing Price}_{i(t-1)}}{\text{Closing Price}_{i(t-1)}}$

Panel Data Multiple Regression Estimation

The approach that can be taken in estimating panel data multiple regression which is a combination of time series data and cross section data is to use analysis:

1. Common Effect Model (CEM)
2. Fixed Effect Model (FEM)
3. Random Effect Model (REM)

Model Selection Test

By using the three basic analyzes above, you can then carry out three model suitability testing procedures to be used in selecting the best panel data multiple regression model as follows:

Chow Test

This test uses F-statistics to determine the choice between the Common Effect model or the Fixed Effect model. Rejection or acceptance of the hypothesis is based on the level $\alpha = 5\%$ in the null hypothesis H_0 and alternative hypothesis H_a .

Between these two models technically compares the calculation of F-statistics with F-table. If from the results of F count > from F table rejection can be made of the null hypothesis H_0 and conversely acceptance can be made of the alternative hypothesis H_a so the appropriate model to use is the Fixed Effect Model, if the results are different then vice versa..

Hausman Test

Hausman testing will determine the choice between the Fixed Effect Model or Random Effect Model. This Hausman test uses the Chi-Square statistical distribution with k degrees of freedom as the number of exogenous variables.

Hypothesis testing against the Hausman test which accepts the null hypothesis H_0 and rejects the alternative hypothesis H_a will be fit using the Random Effect Model, but on the contrary will use the Fixed Effect Model if the statistical hypothesis rejects the null hypothesis H_0 and accepts the alternative hypothesis H_a .

Lagrange Multiplier (LM) Test

Testing the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) is intended to determine the fit model between the Common Effect Model or Random Effect Model. The basis used in this LM test is the Chi-Squares distribution with a degree of freedom equal to the number of exogenous variables.

If the LM statistical value is greater than the critical value of the Chi-Squares statistic, it will reject the null hypothesis H_0 and accept the alternative hypothesis H_a , this result means that the fit estimate is using the Random Effect Model. On the other hand, if the LM statistic value is smaller than the critical value of the Chi-Squares statistic, it will accept the null hypothesis H_0 and reject the alternative hypothesis H_a , this means that the use of the Common Effect Model is more appropriate.

Carrying out the conformity test as explained above can be simplified by looking at Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Model Fit Test

**Panel Data Regression Model
Structural Equation Research Model I,**

$$DER_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 ROA_{it} + \beta_2 EPS_{it} + \beta_3 CR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}; \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$i = 1,2,\dots\dots\dots, N; \quad t = 1,2,\dots\dots\dots T$$

Structural Equation Research Model II,

$$SR_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 ROA_{it} + \beta_2 EPS_{it} + \beta_3 CR_{it} + DER_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}; \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$i = 1,2,\dots\dots\dots, N; \quad t = 1,2,\dots\dots\dots T$$

Where:

DER	=	Debt to Equity Ratio	β	=	Slope
ROA	=	Return On Assets	α	=	Intercept
EPS	=	Earnings Per-Share	N	=	Number of Observations
CR	=	Current Ratio	T	=	Lots of time
SR	=	Stock Return	N x T	=	Number of Panel Data
ε	=	Error component			

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Observations
RS	7.043973	7.008024	11.03570	3.158445	1.812861	135
ROA	0.223691	0.190200	0.934900	0.062500	0.144848	135
EPS	0.323773	0.249525	1.497100	0.008100	0.258545	135
CR	15.86461	7.724650	32.83650	4.870141	11.20828	135
DER	0.360408	0.137858	2.753300	0.003634	0.513796	135

Source: Data processed

Table 3: Multicollinearity

	ROA	EPS	CR	DER
ROA	1.000000	0.327272	-0.413550	-0.359077
EPS	0.327272	1.000000	0.225056	0.035385
CR	-0.413550	0.225056	1.000000	0.691317
DER	-0.359077	0.035385	0.691317	1.000000

Source: Data processed

Research Results Model 1 and 2

B. Leverage and Stock Return as Endogenous Variables in Testing the Suitability of Research Models

Structural Equation 1 and 2 Research Model

Table 4: Chow Test

Research Model 1 Chow Test: Common Effect Vs Fixed Effect Endogenous Variable: Capital Structure				Research Model 2 Chow Test: Common Effect Vs Fixed Effect Endogenous Variable: Stock Return			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.	Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	8.450871	(26,105)	0.0000	Cross-section F	8.238919	(26,104)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	152.416492	26	0.0000	Cross-section Chi-square	150.974095	26	0.0000

Source: Data processed

The results of testing the Chow-test in Research Model 1 and Research Model 2 show that the F test statistics with the chi-square test produce statistical hypotheses: rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$. This can be interpreted as saying that **the Fixed Effect Model** will be better used than the Common Effect Model (Table-4).

Table 5: Hausman Test

Research Model 1 Hausman Test: Fixed Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Capital Structure				Research Model 2 Hausman Test: Fixed Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Stock Return			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.	Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	31.531524	3	0.0000	Cross-section random	31.016825	4	0.0000

Source: Data processed

The same results in testing the Hausman-test in Research Model 1 and Research Model 2 are the F test statistics with chi-square test with statistical hypothesis results: rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$. This means that the same test results can also be said that the use of **the Fixed Effect Model** in the results of this test is better than the Random Effect Model (Table-5).

Table 6: Endogenous Variable: Capital Structure (DER)

Total pool (balanced) observations: 135

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.265242	0.691304	1.830225	0.0701
ROA	3.783936	0.968103	3.908607	0.0002
EPS	-0.384041	0.461985	-0.831284	0.4077
CR	0.318737	0.042192	7.554510	0.0000
Adjusted R-squared	0.704095			
F-statistic	11.99476			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Data processed

Table 7: Fixed Effects (Cross)

Endogenous Variable: Capital Structure (DER)

Total pool (balanced) observations: 135

Trading Code	Coefficient	Trading Code	Coefficient
ADRO--C	-3.741385	KLBF--C	3.926872
AKRA--C	-3.315721	LPPF--C	3.040153
ASII--C	-4.846182	MNCN--C	3.439297
BBCA--C	-2.271573	PGAS--C	3.372340
BBNI--C	-2.455682	PTBA--C	1.325814
BBRI--C	-2.379935	PTPP--C	2.162470
BBTN--C	-2.274875	SCMA--C	2.693178
BMRI--C	-4.089049	SMGR--C	2.683943
BSDE--C	-3.536727	TLKM--C	1.268560
GGRM--C	-2.705949	UNTR--C	0.879777
ICBP--C	-1.284173	UNVR--C	-0.915768
INDF--C	2.552750	WIKA--C	2.208834
INTP--C	2.087394	WSKT--C	1.465215
JSMR--C	0.710422		

Source: Data processed

Table 8: Endogenous Variable: Stock Return (SR)

Total pool (balanced) observations: 135

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.280880	0.696344	1.839436	0.0687
ROA	3.777945	0.972550	3.884576	0.0002
EPS	-0.404179	0.468988	-0.861810	0.3908
CR	0.319977	0.042584	7.514092	0.0000
DER	-0.076156	0.257819	-0.295384	0.7683
Adjusted R-squared	0.701500			
F-statistic	11.49705			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Data processed

Table 9: Fixed Effects (Cross)

Endogenous Variable: Stock Return (SR)

Total pool (balanced) observations: 135

Trading Code	Coefficient	Trading Code	Coefficient
ADRO--C	-3.717923	KLBF--C	3.912104
AKRA--C	-3.296580	LPPF--C	3.036185
ASII--C	-4.823149	MNCN--C	3.426742
BBCA--C	-2.287512	PGAS--C	3.359418
BBNI--C	-2.405161	PTBA--C	1.320008
BBRI--C	-2.352164	PTPP--C	2.148958
BBTN--C	-2.279090	SCMA--C	2.684858
BMRI--C	-4.058569	SMGR--C	2.669980
BSDE--C	-3.513992	TLKM--C	1.253271
GGRM--C	-2.704369	UNTR--C	0.863945
ICBP--C	-1.277712	UNVR--C	-0.928353
INDF--C	2.542535	WIKA--C	2.191245
INTP--C	2.078031	WSKT--C	1.453890
JSMR--C	0.703405		

Source: Data processed

1. Company financial performance (ROA) has a significant effect on Company's Capital Structure (DER) with a positive correlation as seen in table 6
2. Shareholders' income (EPS) has no significant effect on Company's Capital Structure (DER) as seen in table 6
3. Company liquidity (CR) has a significant effect on Company's Capital Structure (DER) with a positive correlation as seen in table 6.
4. In this first research model, the dominant level among the three variables is Company Financial Performance (ROA) as seen in table 6.
5. This study also shows that among the cross-sectional used, the dominant level is in Astra International Tbk with the trade code ASII as seen in table 7.
6. The first research model is suitable for use as the results of the F test are significant at the F-statistic level of 11.99476 (table 6).
7. The use of three exogenous variables in this first research model can explain endogenous variables as the results of the Adjusted R-squared are 70.41% (table 6).
8. Company financial performance (ROA) has a significant effect on Market Appreciation (SR) with a positive correlation as shown in table 8.
9. Shareholders' income (EPS) has an insignificant effect on Market Appreciation (SR) as shown in table 8.
10. Company liquidity (CR) has a significant effect on Market Appreciation (SR) with a positive correlation as shown in table 8.

11. In this second research model, the dominant level among the four variables is Company Financial Performance (ROA) as shown in table 8.
12. The second research model is feasible to use with a significant F test at the F-statistic level of 11.49705 (table 8).
13. The use of the four exogenous variables in this second research model can explain the Adjusted R-squared result of 70.15% (table 8).
14. The intervening variable company's capital structure used shows results that are unable to explain its effect on Market Appreciation (SR)-(table 8).

DISCUSSION

The exogenous variable Company Financial Performance (ROA) used in this study can explain its influence on the endogenous variable Company Capital Structure and the endogenous variable Market Appreciation with a positive correlation. This result supports what was produced in the research of Mulyani (2014), Anwaar (2016), Salamat and Mustafa (2016), Wijaya (2014), but is different from the research results of Sudarsono and Sudiyatno (2016), Mahmudah and Suwitho (2016).

This can be explained by the fact that increasing profitability does not necessarily reduce the amount of debt obligations, but the market responds well with an increase in Market Appreciation. The results of this study are that increasing profitability will increase debt and the analysis that can be done is that increasing profitability can be used to pay dividends, strengthen the working capital position. If this happens, retained earnings will decrease, while asset growth will increase through additional investment, so that what happens from the results of this study is an increase in profitability, not a priority for reducing debt obligations.

Considering that Company Capital Structure cannot explain its influence on Market Appreciation, the results of this study can be said that this variable cannot mediate Market Appreciation. This means that market reactions to obtain returns do not require Company Capital Structure analysis but rather Company Financial Performance (ROA) and Company Liquidity (CR). The results of this study contradict the results of research by Anisa (2015), Sudarsono & Sudiyatno (2016), Putri & Sampurno (2012), but support the results of research by Haanurat (2013), Legiman et. al. (2015), Subalno (2010), Wulandari et al. (2017), Hatfield et al. (1994).

Shareholders' Income (EPS) in this study cannot explain its influence on Market Appreciation directly or indirectly through Company Capital Structure as an intervening variable. These results can be said that the profitability paid as cash dividends is not too dominant because it is not responded to by the market, so that the increase in profitability is more intended for business expansion or investment. This fact illustrates that the type of investors on the Indonesia Stock Exchange is more short-term. The results of this study contradict the results of research by Gejali and Satrio (2013), Khan et al. (2013), Salamat and Mustafa (2016), Anwaar (2016), Aisah and Mandala (2016), but support the results of research by Wijaya (2014) and Karim

(2015). The exogenous variable Company Liquidity (CR) can explain its influence on Market Appreciation directly and indirectly through Company Capital Structure where both are positively correlated. This can be explained still related to the explanation of profitability in the paragraph above. The results of this study indicate that the higher the availability of liquidity from profitability results will actually increase liabilities and not reduce liabilities. These results can be interpreted that the availability of liquidity is greater for other financial settlements than for paying debt obligations. These results support the results of Nastiti's research (2016) and differ from the research of Bhattarai (2016), Verena and Haryanto (2013), Sheikh and Zongjun (2011), Nugrahani and Sampurno (2010).

The exogenous variables in the results of this study were only able to explain the endogenous variables in each research model by 70.41% (model 1) and 70.15% (model 2), so that the addition of exogenous variables can still be done by further researchers.

CONCLUSION

Findings: The results of this study conclude that Company Financial Performance (ROA) has a significant effect on Market Appreciation (SR) without mediation from Company Capital Structure (DER). The same result also occurs when the Company Liquidity variable has a significant effect on Market Appreciation (SR) without using mediation from Company Capital Structure (DER). Among the Exogenous variables, the dominant or most sensitive of the two research models is Company Financial Performance (ROA) and the dominant or most sensitive Cross section is Astra International Tbk with the trading code (ASII).

Acknowledgments

Thanks to colleagues who have helped in conducting this research. Hopefully in the future we can conduct research with the ideas needed by the people in need.

References

- 1) Adi, R., P. (2017), The Influence of Asset Structure, Company Size, and Profitability on Capital Structure in Pharmaceutical Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange. *Bilancia*, 427.
- 2) Anisa, N. (2015), Analysis of Factors that Influence Stock Returns (Case Study of Automotive and Components Sub-Sector Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2010-2014 Period), *Perbanas Review*, 1(1), 72– 86.
- 3) Anwaar, Maryyam (2016), Impact of Firms' Performance on Stock Returns (Evidence from Listed Companies of FTSE-100 Index London, UK). *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: Accounting and Auditing*, Vol. 16, Issue 1, Version 1.0.
- 4) Anwaar, Maryyam (2016), Impact of Firms' Performance on Stock Returns (Evidence from Listed Companies of FTSE-100 Index London, UK). *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: Accounting and Auditing*, Vol. 16, Issue 1, Version 1.0. Aisah dan Mandala (2016),
- 5) Bararoh, Tantri (2015), Analysis of Fundamental Factors, Foreign Exchange and Interest Rate on Stock Return (Studies in Manufacturing Companies Listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange for 2011-2013 Periods). *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, Vol. 4, Issue 2, PP. 36-42. Utami et al. (2015),

- 6) Bhattarai, Y., (2016), Effect of Liquidity on The Capital Structure of Nepalese Manufacturing Companies. *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, Volume 4, Issue 3.
- 7) Carlo, M. A. 2014, The Influence of Return on Equity, Dividend Payout Ratio, and Price to Earnings Ratio on Stock Returns, *E-Jurnal Akuntansi*.7(1): 151-164.
- 8) Devaki, A., (2017), Factors that Influence Stock Returns in LQ-45 Companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange, *Benefita Journal: Development Economics, Business Management & Accounting*, 2(2), 157–168.
- 9) Fama, E., F., (1970), Efficient Capital Markets: A Review of Theory and Empirical Work, *Journal of Finance*, Vol. 25, No. 2, May, 1970, Papers and Proceedings of the Twenty-Eighth Annual Meeting of the American Finance Association New York, N.Y. December, 28-30, 1969
- 10) Febriana, Febby and Sulistiana, Indra (2024), The Effect of EPS and ROA on Stock Returns in the Food and Beverage Sector for the Period 2021-2023 on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, Vol. 3 No. 1
- 11) Febriana, Febby and Sulistiana, Indra (2024), The Effect of EPS and ROA on Stock Returns in the Food and Beverage Sector for the Period 2021-2023 on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen (KARIR)*, Volume 3, No.1, April 2024.
- 12) Fitriarningsih, Dwi et.al., (2022), Analysis of the Effect of Earning Per-Share, Economic Value Added on Stock Returns during the Covid19 Pandemic.
- 13) Gejali, Ivan Andrianto & Budhi Satrio (2013), The Influence of Current Ratio, Return On Equity, and Earning Per Share on Stock Returns, *Jurnal Ilmu & Riset Manajemen*, Vol. 2, No. 6: 1-15.
- 14) Haanurat, A. I. (2013), The Influence of Company Characteristics and Macroeconomics on the Return of Syaria Stocks Listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index, *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 3(2), 115-134.,
- 15) Haanurat, A. I. (2013), The Influence of Company Characteristics and Macroeconomics on the Return of Sharia Stocks Listed on the Jakarta Islamic Index, *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 3(2), 115–134.
- 16) Hatfield, G. B., Cheng, L. T. W., & Davidson, W. N. (1994). The Determination of Optimal Capital Structure: The Effect of Firm and Industry Debt Ratios on Market Value. *Journal of Financial and Strategic Decisions*, 7(3), 1–14.
- 17) Karim, Abdul (2015), Analysis of the Influence of Internal and External Factors on Stock Returns of Manufacturing Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) for the 2010-2012 Period, *Media Ekonomi dan Manajemen*, Vol. 30 No.1.
- 18) Khan, Wajid, Arab Naz, Madiha Khan, Waseem Khan Qaiser Khan, and Shabeer Ahmad (2013), The Impact of Capital Structure and Financial Performance on Stock Returns “A Case of Pakistan Textile Industry”. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 6 (2): 289-295. Salamat dan Mustafa (2016),
- 19) Legiman, F. M., Tommy, P., & Untu, V. (2015), Factors that Influence Share Returns in Agroindustry Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2009-2012 Period, *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen Bisnis Dan Akuntansi (EMBA)*, 3(3), 382–392.
- 20) Legiman, F. M., Tommy, P., & Untu, V., (2015), Factors that Influence Stock Returns in Agro-industrial Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2009-2012 Period, *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi (EMBA)*, 3(3), 382–392.
- 21) Mahmudah, Umrotul, & Suwitho (2016), The influence of ROA, firm size, and NPM on stock returns in cement companies, *Jurnal Ilmu dan Riset Manajemen*, Vol. 5, No. 1: 1-15.
- 22) Margaretha, F., Damayanti, I. (2008), The Influence of Price Earnings Ratio, Dividend Yield and Market to Book Ratio on Stock Returns on the Indonesian Stock Exchange, *Jurnal Bisnis Dan Akuntansi Akuntansi*.10(3): 149-160.

- 23) Masa'deh, R., Tayeh, M., Al-Jarrah, I., & Tarhini, A. (2015), Accounting vs. Market-based Measures of Firm Performance Related to Information Technology Investments. *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*.9(1): 129-145. Retrieved from http://www.irssh.com/yahoo_site_admin/assets/docs/12_IRSSH-1114-V9N1.115111327.
- 24) Mayuni, IAI and Suarjaya, Gede (2018), The Influence of ROA, Firm Size, EPS, and PER on Stock Returns in the Manufacturing Sector at BEI, *E-Journal of Management*, Udayana University, Vol 7 No 8. DOI: 10.24843/EJMUNUD.2018.v07.i08.p02.
- 25) Muhammad, N., & Scrimgeour, F. (2014), Stock Returns and Fundamentals in the Australian Market. *Asian Journal of Finance & Accounting*.6(1): 271-290. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ajfa.v6i1.5486>
- 26) Mulyani, H., S. (2014), The Effect of Profitability and Sales Growth on Capital Structure, Faculty of Economics UNMA.
- 27) Nastiti, R., D., (2016), The Influence of Asset Structure, Liquidity, Profitability, Company Size, Sales Growth on Capital Structure, *Jurnal Ilmu dan Riset Akuntansi* : Volume 5, Nomor 1.
- 28) Nurrohman MHN and Zulaikha (2013), The Effect of Earning Per-Share, Stock Return, Audit Quality, and Profit Results on Stock Returns One Year Ahead (Empirical Study of Manufacturing Companies Listed on the IDX in 2010-201), *Diponegoro Journal of Accounting*, Volume 2, Number 3.
- 29) Purwohandoko (2017), The Influence of Firm's Size, Growth, and Profitability on Firm Value with Capital Structure as the Mediator: A Study on the Agricultural Firms Listed in the Indonesian Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Economics and Finance* , Vol. 9, No. 8.
- 30) Puspitasari, A., & Purnamasari, L., (2013), The Effect of Changes in the Dividend Payout Ratio and Dividend Yield on Stock Returns (Study of Manufacturing Companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange), *Journal of Business and Banking*, 3(2), 213–222.
- 31) Putri, A. A. B., & Sampurno, R. D. (2012), Analysis of the Effect of Return on Assets, Earning Per Share, Net Profit Margin and Debt to Equity Ratio on Stock Returns (Case Study of the Real Estate and Property Industry Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2007 - 2009 Period), *Diponegoro Business Review*, 1(1), 1–11.
- 32) Putri, A. A. B., & Sampurno, R. D. (2012). Analysis of the Effect of Return on Assets, Earning Per Share, Net Profit Margin and Debt to Equity Ratio on Stock Returns (Case Study of the Real Estate and Property Industry Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2007–2009 Period), *Diponegoro Business Review*, 1(1), 1–11.
- 33) Salamat, Wasfi A. Al., Haneen H. H. Mustafa (2016), The Impact of Capital Structure on Stock Return: Empirical Evidence from Amman Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Business, and Social Science*, Vol. 7, No.9: 183-196.
- 34) Sayidah, N., & Handayani, A. E. (2017), The Effect of Institutional Ownership on Dividend Information Content, *Jurnal Analisa Akuntansi Dan Perpajakan*, 1(1), 107–115.
- 35) Shefrin, H., M. Statman (1998), The disposition to sell winners too early and ride losers too long: Theory and evidence. *The Journal of Finance*, 40(3), 777-790.
- 36) Sheikh, Nadeem, Ahmad. & Wang, Zongjun (2011), Determinants of Capital Structure, an Empirical Study of Firm in Manufacturing Industry of Pakistan. *Internasional Journal of Managerial Finance*. 37(2): pp: 117-133.
- 37) Sinambela, Elizar (2013), The Effect of Earning Per Share (Eps) on Stock Returns in Property and Real Estate Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, *Journal of Economics and Development Studies (Ekonomikawan)*, Vol 13, No 1.

- 38) Subalno, S. (2010), Analysis of the Influence of Fundamental Factors and Economic Conditions on Stock Returns, Case Study of Automotive and Component Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2003-2007 Period, *Orbith*, 6(1).
- 39) Subalno, S. (2010). Analysis of the Influence of Fundamental Factors and Economic Conditions on Stock Returns, Case Study of Automotive and Component Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2003-2007 Period, *Orbith*, 6(1).
- 40) Sudarsono, B., & Sudiyatno, B. (2016). Factors that Influence Share Returns in Property and Real Estate Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange 2009-2014, *Jurnal Bisnis Dan Ekonomi*, 23(1).
- 41) Sudarsono, B., & Sudiyatno, B., (2016), Factors that Influence Share Returns in Property and Real Estate Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange 2009 – 2014, *Jurnal Bisnis Dan Ekonomi*, 23(1).
- 42) Sudarsono, Bambang, & Bambang Sudiyatno (2016), Factors that Influence Share Returns in Property and Real Estate Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange 2009 – 2014, *Jurnal Bisnis dan Ekonomi (JBE)*, Vol. 23, No. 1, Hal. 30-51.
- 43) Utami, F., & Murwaningsari, E. (2017), Analysis of the Effect of Profitability Ratios on Stock Returns with Dividend Policy as a Moderating Variable (Empirical Study of Manufacturing Companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2021-2015 Period), *Jurnal Magister Akuntansi Trisakti (e-Journal)*, 4(1), 75– 94.
- 44) Verena, Sari. & Haryonto, Mulyo (2013), The Influence of Profitability, Asset Growth, Company Size, Asset Structure and Liquidity on Capital Structure in Manufacturing Companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange in 2008-2010, *Diponegoro Journal Of Management*. 2(3): pp: 1-11.
- 45) Wijaya, Yusuf (2014), Factors that Influence Stock Returns in Manufacturing Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange, *Jurnal Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, Vol. 16, No. 1a, Is. 9: 1-18.
- 46) Wijaya, Yusuf (2014), Factors that Influence Stock Returns in Manufacturing Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange, *Jurnal Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, Vol. 16, No. 1a, Is. 9: 1-18.
- 47) Wulandari, E. S., Sunarko, B., & Tohir, T. (2017), Determinants of capital structure and its influence on stock returns in the goods and consumer goods industry listed on the IDX, *Performance*, 24(1), 13–24.
- 48) Wulandari, E. S., Sunarko, B., & Tohir, T., (2017), Determinants of Capital Structure and Its Influence on Stock Returns in the Goods and Consumer Industry listed on the IDX, *Performance*, 24(1), 13–24.
- 49) Zeytino, E., Akarim, Y. D., & Çelik, S. (2012), The Impact of Market-Based Ratios on Stock Returns: The Evidence from Insurance Sector in Turkey. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*. 84(84): 41-48.